

Development of high yielding ethanol resistant strain of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* for ethanol production

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Abstract : *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB, an ethanol producing strain (4.0%) was treated with 10%, 15% and 20% ethanol for 30, 60 and 180 min. Only 5.5% colonies isolated by 30 min incubation in 10% ethanol gave higher alcohol production (7.5%) than the parent strains. These strains when incubated in 15% alcohol for 60 min then only 4.5% alcohol resistant strains gave higher alcohol production (9.5%) than the parent strains. On further exposure to 20% ethanol, there was a decrease in alcohol production.

Keywords : *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB, alcohol resistance.

Introduction

In view of increasing importance of alcohol as an alternative resource for chemicals and liquid fuel, a great deal of research interest in ethanol fermentation has been generated in recent years¹⁻⁵. The major areas of research interests in ethanol fermentation have been : (i) increased ethanol concentration and specific ethanol production rate, (ii) improvement of ethanol tolerance of yeast⁶⁻⁹ and (iii) development of continuous ethanol fermentation process using high density cell culture¹⁰. In India, due to rising cost of petroleum and the rate of depletion of fluid fossil fuel resources, it is necessary to produce more and more ethanol from agricultural carbohydrate products to satisfy the fuel consumption demand and other chemical industries need¹¹⁻¹⁷.

The present paper deals with the development of high yielding ethanol resistant strains of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* to increase the rate of production of ethanol from carbohydrate materials.

Results and discussion

(A) Isolation of 10% ethanol resistant strains of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB : The cell suspension of the

parent strain, containing 2.4×10^7 cells/ml, was then treated with 10% ethanol for 30, 60 and 180 min of incubation at 30 °C. After incubation for 30, 60 and 180 min, the cell suspension in each case was diluted and plated out on YPD agar medium 570 isolates were selected from different stages of treatment with 10% ethanol for ethanol production. It was observed that the *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB 510, gave higher yield of ethanol (7.5%) than the parent strain (4.0%) in medium I. The results are shown in Fig. 1 and Table 1.

A total of 570 colonies were isolated during the incubation in 10% ethanol. It appears from Table 1 and Fig. 1 that the maximum number of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB is killed in 10% ethanol during 180 min incubation. Only 5.5% of 10% ethanol resistant strains obtained during 30 min incubation gives more ethanol production (7.5%) than the parent strain (4.0%) whereas maximum killing takes place in 180 min incubation. So there is no correlation between the maximum killing and the isolation of more positive variants for higher ethanol production than the parent strain.

(B) Isolation of 15% ethanol resistant strains of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB 510 : The cell suspension of

Fig. 1. Effect of ethanol production of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB for different periods of incubation in 10% ethanol (values were represented as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$, "0" stands for control. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

Table 1. Effect of ethanol production of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB during the incubation in 10% ethanol for 30, 60 and 180 min (values : mean \pm SEM, $n = 6$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.01$)

Time of incubation (min)	Total number of colonies isolated	Percent of parent stain killed	Percent of ethanol production		
			Similar to parent	More than parent	Less than parent
30	185 \pm 5	11.5 \pm 0.2	5.2 \pm 0.1	*5.5 \pm 0.05	89.3 \pm 0.9
60	215 \pm 2	26.0 \pm 0.8	17.0 \pm 0.2	*3.0 \pm 0.02	80.0 \pm 1.5
180	170 \pm 4	42.0 \pm 1	12.5 \pm 0.5	**4.2 \pm 0.06	83.3 \pm 2.03

this 10% ethanol resistant strain, containing 2.4×10^7 cells/ml, was then treated with 15% ethanol for 30, 60 and 180 min of incubation at 30 °C. After incubation for 30, 60 and 180 min, the cell suspension in each case was diluted and plated on YPD agar medium. 545 isolates were selected from different stages of treatment with 15% ethanol for further ethanol production. It was observed that the resistant strain *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB 910, gives higher yield of ethanol (95%) in medium I. The results are shown in Fig. 2 and Table 2.

A total of 545 colonies were isolated during the incubation at 30, 60 and 180 min in 15% ethanol. It shows from Table 2 and Fig. 2 that the maximum number of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB 510 is killed in 15% etha-

nol during 180 min incubation. Only 4.5% of 15% ethanol resistant strains obtained during 60 min incubation gives more ethanol production (95%) than the parent strains (7.5%). Table 2 also shows that there is no correlation between the maximum killing and the isolation of more positive variants for higher ethanol production than the parent strains. These high yielding strains were found stable in subsequent fermentation trials.

(C) *Isolation of 20% ethanol resistant strains of Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB 910 : The cell suspension of this 15% ethanol resistant strain, containing 2.4×10^7 cells/ml, was then treated with 20% ethanol for 30, 60 and 180 min of incubation at 30 °C. After incubation for 30, 60 and 180 min, the cell suspension in each case was

Fig. 2. Effect of ethanol production of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB 510 for different periods of incubation in 15% ethanol (values were represented as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$, "0" stands for control. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

Table 2. Effect of ethanol production of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB 510 during the incubation in 15% ethanol for 30, 60 and 180 min (values : mean \pm SEM, $n = 6$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.01$)

Time of incubation (min)	Total number of colonies isolated	Percent of parent stain killed	Percent of ethanol production		
			Similar to parent	More than parent	Less than parent
30	175 \pm 2	42.2 \pm 0.4	12.5 \pm 0.1	*4.0 \pm 0.04	83.5 \pm 2
60	210 \pm 5	62.5 \pm 0.8	6.0 \pm 0.08	**4.5 \pm 0.06	89.5 \pm 2.9
180	160 \pm 4	76.2 \pm 1	11.0 \pm 0.1	*4.2 \pm 0.03	84.8 \pm 3.4

diluted and plated out on YPD agar medium. 355 isolates were selected from different stages of treatment with 20% ethanol for ethanol production. It was observed that the strains isolated from 20% ethanol incubated for 30, 60 and 180 min gave lower yield of ethanol than the 10% and 15% ethanol resistant strains. The results are shown in Fig. 3 and Table 3.

During the incubation in 20% ethanol for 30, 60 and 180 min, a total of 355 colonies of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB 910 were isolated. Table 3 and Fig. 3 indicates that the maximum killing takes place during 180 min incubation and all isolated strains give lower ethanol production than the parent strains. So the 20% ethanol incubation is not suitable for the isolation of high yielding alcohol producing strains although the lethal effect is

higher than the 10% and 15% ethanol incubation.

In the present studies, we have observed the superiority of 10% and 15% ethanol resistant strains for higher alcohol production than the 20% ethanol resistant strains although lethal effects are lower.

Further studies are in progress to test this culture for the development of temperature resistant strains and to assess its industrial utilization for large scale alcohol production.

Experimental

Microorganism : The yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB used in this study was isolated from the environment (North Bengal pineapple waste disposal material). This strain was used for the development of high alcohol resis-

Fig. 3. Effect of ethanol production of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB 910 for different periods of incubation in 20% ethanol (values were represented as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$, "0" stands for control. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

Table 3. Effect of ethanol production of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB 910 during the incubation in 20% ethanol for 30, 60 and 180 min (values : mean \pm SEM, $n = 6$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.01$)

Time of incubation (min)	Total number of colonies isolated	Percent of parent stain killed	Percent of ethanol production		
			Similar to parent	More than parent	Less than parent
30	140 \pm 5	87.0 \pm 1.9	0	0	100 \pm 2
60	125 \pm 2	88.2 \pm 2.6	0	0	100 \pm 4
180	90 \pm 1	95.2 \pm 3.2	0	0	100 \pm 1

tant strains using 10%, 15% and 20% ethanol. The time of incubation of yeast in each concentration was 30, 60 and 180 min. In the course of development of ethanol resistant strains by using the above mentioned ethanol concentrations, 1470 resistant strains were isolated. Out of these resistant strains only *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB 910 which produced 9.5% alcohol, was selected for further studies.

Medium and cultural condition : The parent culture, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB which produced 4.0% alcohol and alcohol resistant strains were maintained in YPD agar medium (1% yeast extract, 2% peptone, 2% dextrose and 3% agar, pH 5.0) slants at 4 °C. This medium was also used for the development of alcohol resis-

tant strains studies. The medium I used for the fermentative production of ethanol contained sucrose, 10%; KH_2PO_4 , 0.1%; $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, 0.5%; $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.05% yeast extract, 0.1%; pH 4.5. Sucrose was sterilized separately and then added to the medium before incubation. When the cultures were needed for alcohol resistant strains development, they were transferred to slants of yeast extract, peptone and dextrose agar medium and incubated at 30 °C for 24 h. The yeast cells were harvested by washing the slant with sterile distilled water and filtering the resulting cell suspension through several layers of absorbent cotton. The cell density was adjusted to 2.4×10^7 cells/ml of the suspension. This cell suspension was used both for alcohol resistant strains development stud-

ies and for the inoculation of the fermentation medium. Surface culture fermentations were carried out using medium 500 ml Erlenmeyer conical flasks, each containing 150 ml of medium I. The flasks were then incubated at 28 °C for 48 h.

Determination of ethanol concentration : After alcoholic fermentation, the ethanol produced was determined by Gas Chromatography (Pye Unicam series 104) with flame ionizing detector (FID) on a column of Porapak Q using nitrogen as carrier gas. The column temperature and detector temperature were 190 °C and 230 °C respectively. In each case 5 µL of sample was injected¹⁸.

The quantitative calculation of ethanol concentration was made by measuring the peak areas of the sample in calibration relative to the internal standard. *n*-Propanol was used as internal standard.

Fermentable and nonfermentable sucrose was monitored by AOAC method¹⁸.

Statistical analysis : Data were presented as the mean of at least six independent experiments along with SEM [(mean ±SEM), where *n* = 6]. Statistical analysis of data was done by Student's *t* test, by using MS Excel. A "p" value less than 0.05 was considered significant and less than 0.01 as a highly significant.

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